

From radiography to CT: Geometric calibration using a 3D-printed phantom

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ABSTRACT

X-ray imaging is a widely utilised non-destructive technique in both medical and industrial applications. Contemporary advancements, such as computed tomography (CT), enable the reconstruction of three-dimensional representations of internal structures from multiple projection angles. This study presents the development of a compact and functional CT system based on a portable X-ray source and a digital detector. A key component of the system is a custom-designed calibration phantom manufactured using 3D printing and incorporating precisely arranged steel spheres. Geometric calibration is performed using an iterative optimization approach based on sphere projections acquired from multiple viewing angles. The proposed method achieves sub-pixel calibration accuracy, with residual geometric deviations consistently below approximately one-fifth of a detector pixel. The impact of calibration is demonstrated by a clear reduction of geometry-induced artifacts and an improvement in reconstruction consistency compared to the uncalibrated case. The complete spatial configuration of the system, including source, object, and detector alignment, is explicitly described, enabling reproducibility and facilitating further development. The proposed setup supports reliable qualitative tomographic imaging with minimal hardware requirements, thereby promoting the wider adoption of mobile and cost-effective CT technologies for field and industrial applications.

1. Introduction

X-ray imaging is one of the most widely used and reliable methods of non-destructive visualisation in both the medical and industrial fields [1]. This technique involves transmitting X-rays through materials, where varying densities and compositions of sample structures cause different levels of radiation absorption [2]. Computed Tomography (CT) scanning, in particular, represents a significant breakthrough by providing three-dimensional reconstructions from multiple projection angles, thus overcoming the limitations of two-dimensional imaging [3]. In recent times, there has been an increased focus on imaging modalities that require high spatial accuracy and quantitative capabilities. Nevertheless, the elevated cost and complexity of dedicated CT systems remain a significant barrier, particularly for smaller laboratories and institutions with limited funding. Consequently, there is increasing interest in low-cost, portable alternatives that can deliver sufficient geometric precision while remaining accessible to a broader range of users.

The impetus for this research is to reduce the cost and improve the accessibility of computed tomography, enabling its practical deployment in low-cost, portable systems. Inexpensive custom solutions which adapt older CT hardware [4] or radiographic devices for CT scans [5–7] are sought after in fields from medicine [4,8] to cultural heritage [7] and industry [5,6,9] with the goal to improve the general accessibility of this modality and the advanced sample inspection it enables. The present study focuses on the development of a fully functional CT system that combines a portable X-ray source with a digital detector. A fundamental element of the configuration process pertains to geometric calibration, a prerequisite for the precise reconstruction of the internal structures of scanned objects. To this end, a calibration phantom composed of ball bearings is employed, arranged in a well-defined geometric layout within a 3D-printed structure. By analysing how these spheres appear at different projection angles, the geometry of the imaging system can be determined retrospectively. Initial distances between the source, the rotation axis, and the detector are measured approximately using

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Nomenclature	
<i>SOD</i>	Source-Object Distance, can also be marked as SRD (source-to-rotation axis distance)
<i>ODD</i>	Object-Detector Distance
<i>SDD</i>	Source-Detector Distance
<i>ds</i>	the distance between the center of projection and the center of the sphere
<i>ds_p</i>	distance of the center of projection and projection of the center of the sphere
<i>S</i>	the center of the sphere
<i>S_d</i>	projection of the centre of the sphere into the detector plane, which is offset from the ideal position by the angle θ_o
<i>S_p</i>	projection of the centre of the sphere into the detector plane, which has an ideal position, i.e. the coordinate axis of the detector <i>z</i> lies in this plane
<i>r_s</i>	radius of the sphere
\vec{n}_d	normal vector of the detector plane
α	the angle between the perpendicular to the detector plane and the line through the center of the projection and the center of the sphere
β	half of the visual angle of the sphere
<i>a_p</i>	major semi-axis of the ellipse (projection of the sphere onto the detector plane)
<i>b_p</i>	minor semi-axis of the ellipse (projection of the sphere onto the detector plane)
$[x_e, y_e]$	coordinate of the general point of the ellipse
<i>A, B</i>	points on the surface of the sphere where the lines defining the field of view tangentially touch the sphere
<i>A_p, B_p</i>	projection of tangent points A, B, which form the main axis of the ellipse (projection of the sphere onto the detector plane)
<i>E_p</i>	the true center of the ellipse (projection of the sphere onto the detector plane)
(x', y', z')	phantom coordinate system
(t, s, r)	the coordinate system of the detector, which has an ideal position, i.e. the detector coordinate axis <i>r</i> lies in detector plane
$[D_x, D_y]$	the point at which the center beam intersects the detector plane in the ideal position (principal point)
<i>o</i>	the projection of the axis of rotation perpendicular to the center beam onto the detector plane
<i>o'</i>	axis of rotation
<i>r_p</i>	projection of the radius of the sphere
<i>O</i>	the point about which the detector rotates from the general position to the position where the projection of the axis of rotation is perpendicular to the central beam
<i>da_p, db_p</i>	distance of the projection of the tangent point <i>A_p, B_p</i> from the origin of the detector coordinate system (t, s, r) , which is perpendicular to the central beam
<i>ds_d</i>	distance of the projection of the center of the sphere <i>S_p</i> from the origin of the detector coordinate system (t, s, r) , which is perpendicular to the central beam
<i>de_p</i>	distance of the true center of the ellipse <i>E_p</i> from the origin of the detector coordinate system (t, s, r) , which is perpendicular to the central beam
\vec{v}_d, \vec{u}_d	direction vectors, which determine the detector plane that is perpendicular to the central beam
θ'_z	angle of offset rotation of the rotary table axis
θ'_o	initial angle of rotation of the phantom during the first projection
θ'_y	angle between the axis of rotation from the detector plane in the ideal position
θ_o	detector tilt angle
<i>d'_o</i>	translation of phantom axis <i>z'</i> from axis of rotation <i>o'</i>
<i>d'_z</i>	translation of the phantom axis <i>z'</i> in the direction of <i>o'</i>
<i>SSD_d[⊥]</i>	perpendicular distance of the projection origin and the projection of the sphere center to the detector plane <i>S_d</i>
θ_e	ellipse orientation angle
$[S_{p_x}, S_{p_y}]$	coordinates of the center of gravity of the ellipse
θ_r	angle of inclination of the rotation axis
<i>S_e</i>	area of the ellipse
AoR	Axis of Rotation

a tape measure. However, calibration with the phantom refines these parameters, significantly improving the accuracy of the reconstructed data. This approach enables the acquisition of high-quality CT images using even rudimentary mobile devices, thereby expanding the practical applications of portable tomography systems.

2. Literature overview

Robust and accurate determination of the scan geometry in CT (geometric calibration) is important for both reliable, artifact-free tomographic reconstruction [1,10] and dimensional accuracy of the reconstructed data [11–13]. This study aims to facilitate the capability of inexpensive qualitative inspection. As such, artifact-free reconstruction is prioritized before dimensional accuracy of the reconstructed data.

Geometric calibration methods vary in the number of degrees of freedom. Methods which determine a single variable are typically used when the scan geometry is known with a sufficiently low degree of error, and only certain non-reproducible parameters, such as the position of the axis of rotation, are optimized for each CT scan [14]. Other methods aim for a more comprehensive multivariate geometric calibration, often with certain case-specific constraints such as the assumption of a circular orbit [10,15].

Methods for multivariate determination of the scan geometry are categorized into four distinct groups. The first group comprises methods which use reference instruments [13,16,17]. These methods are typically reliable but expensive and possibly difficult to implement, especially in field conditions.

The second group includes methods that use radiographs of well-defined phantoms [13,18–20] for determining the scan geometry, often through minimizing reprojection errors [12,13]. These methods are primarily limited by the manufacturing quality of the phantom, which makes them suitable for calibrating larger CT systems, where a sufficient manufacturing precision relative to the size of the phantom and the resolution of the scanner can be easily achieved [10].

Methods in the third group calibrate the scan geometry based on radiographs of fiducial objects with arbitrary placement [10,15,21,22]. Many methods in this category are based on the landmark work of von Smekal et al. [21], which is among the first publications to feature a comprehensive formal analysis of the CT calibration problem. These approaches do not need a precisely manufactured phantom, making them ideal for high-resolution applications [10]. However, the data acquisition and processing steps of geometry determination tend to be more complex in this case, as they rely on additional assumptions such as a

Table 1

Overview of the four categories of CT scan geometry estimation and calibration, which were identified. For a more granular classification of methods in this field, see [26].

Category	Key Features	Advantages	Drawbacks
Reference instruments [13,16,17]	Use of interferometers and other instruments to measure the CT geometry directly	No reference scan required, high reliability, high accuracy	High cost
Well-defined phantoms [12,13,18–20]	Separate calibration measurement using a purpose-made reference object	Standardized procedure, robustness	Limited use in high-resolution applications, separate calibration scan required
Arbitrary fiducial markers [10,15,21,22]	Estimation of scan geometry using reference markers without a predefined arrangement	Single scan for calibration and data acquisition, high-resolution capability, adaptability	Complex calibration problem
Online calibration [23–25]	Geometry calibration using only structures of the scanned sample	No reference scan required	High algorithmic complexity, robustness concerns

perfectly circular scan trajectory [10,15], and, in some cases, omit the correction of less impactful types of distortion [21].

The fourth category comprises online methods, which calibrate the scan geometry from the scanned data themselves. Methods in this category may optimize the scan geometry based on image quality metrics [23–25] or they may utilize fiducial markers scanned alongside the object [7,15,26]. No separate reference scan is required in this case, which makes these methods very versatile and capable of addressing non-reproducible geometric errors [15]. However, the performance of these methods depends strongly on the structures, contrast, and noise within the scanned data [15,19,26], and the methods themselves may require a comparatively large amount of computational time and power [15].

This study aims to perform geometric calibration of an inexpensive radiography system and thus enable low-cost computed tomography in field conditions. The second category of methods (well-defined phantoms) was chosen as the preferred solution of the problem at hand. Calibration using relatively costly reference instruments was dismissed in favor of an inexpensive 3D-printed phantom manufactured using fused deposition modeling (FDM), an accessible and sufficiently precise method for this application. Solutions with arbitrarily distributed fiducial markers were rejected to simplify the analysis of the calibration problem, as their advantage in high-resolution is not relevant in the field conditions considered in this work. Additionally, a defined phantom has the potential to simplify calibration for inexperienced operators. Online methods were abandoned due to their complexity and potential lack of robustness. Methods which use well-defined phantoms are particularly appealing for this application for their robustness, accuracy, and ease of implementation [26]. The main drawback of this method — the requirement of a separate calibration scan of a phantom — is an acceptable tradeoff in this use case. For clarity, an overview of the four categories of geometric calibration methods, including their key features, advantages, and limitations, is summarized in Table 1.

The calibration problem at hand can be approached using a number of the methods mentioned above, with two recent ones being the approaches described by Bossema et al. [7] and Graetz et al. [10]. A separate calibration procedure from these approaches is implemented in this work. Bossema et al. [7] describe a use case which is similar to ours, and they use fiducials distributed around the sample in order to calibrate the scan geometry and acquire tomographic data in a single scan. We opted to perform a reference scan with a defined phantom in order to make the workflow more easily adaptable for different types of samples and avoid low contrast of the fiducial markers in scans of heavier industrial parts. A predefined phantom is also potentially more convenient and readily deployable in field conditions than customized sample holder with fiducial markers. Compared to Graetz et al. [10], the method utilized in this work aims for increased simplicity in terms of both the description of the problem and the calibration scheme itself. The rationale behind this is that a calibration procedure which is described in more elementary terms will be more accessible for opera-

tors of portable radiography devices, who are not closely familiar with CT. Finally, to the authors’ knowledge, no current work in this field presents an approach with an integrated 3D-printed phantom, a combination which also has the potential to improve the accessibility of low-cost field CT setups.

3. Tomographic reconstruction

Transmission X-ray CT is a method for reconstructing the internal structure of an object based on the attenuation of X-ray radiation as it passes through the material [3]. The object is represented by a function of the linear attenuation coefficient μ , which describes the degree of radiation attenuation. Projections, obtained using X-rays, are line integrals of this function along the path of the rays. These projections are used to reconstruct the spatial distribution of μ , enabling the creation of a cross-sectional image of the object [2]. Accurate reconstruction requires precise knowledge of the acquisition geometry, as differences between the assumed and actual geometry can lead to artifacts, unintended distortions or anomalies in the reconstructed image, and degradation of image quality.

3.1. Mathematical principle

Let us consider a two-dimensional object function $f(x, y)$, representing a thin cross-section of a sample, centered at the origin of a Cartesian coordinate system.

Definition 1 (Radon transform). Radon transform \mathcal{R} maps a function $f(x, y)$ defined on \mathbb{R}^2 into the set of its integrals over the hyperplanes of \mathbb{R}^2 . So for $s, t \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\theta \in \langle 0, 2\pi \rangle$ applies

$$\mathcal{R}f(t, \theta) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t, s) ds.$$

The coordinates (t, s) represent a system that has been rotated counterclockwise by an angle θ with respect to the original (x, y) system [2,27]. Projections $p_{\theta}(t) = \mathcal{R}f(t, \theta)$ in X-ray CT are defined as sets of line integrals, where $f(t, s) = \mu(t, s)$ [2]. There are several common ways to form projections from line integrals, differing in geometry and application. The main types are parallel-beam, fan-beam, and cone-beam projections [1].

A parallel-beam projection is a set of parallel line integrals represented as $p_{\theta}(t)$ where θ is a constant angle. For cone-beam projections, it’s useful to first explain line integrals in 3D. A new coordinate system (t, s, r) is created by rotating the (x, y, z) system twice, first by an angle θ around the z axis and then by an angle γ around the t axis [2]. Using this coordinate system, the line integral in 3D can be expressed as

$$p_{\theta,\gamma}(t, r) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(t, s, r) ds.$$

Fig. 1. Geometry of a circular cone-beam CT acquisition. The X-ray source rotates around the object at a distance D from the rotation center. The detector plane ω is parameterized by coordinates (p, q) , with the central ray intersecting the detector at $(0, 0)$. The angle β denotes the source rotation angle. The object coordinate system (x, y, z) is transformed to the projection coordinates (t, s, r) , where s is the integration direction along the ray. For $q = 0$, the geometry reduces to the fan-beam case.

A cone-beam ray can be expressed as $p_\beta(p, q)$ with a virtual detector plane w centered at the origin (it is a scaled-down version of the original detector, which is just moved closer to the source) through relationships

$$\theta = \beta + \arctan \frac{p}{D}, \quad \gamma = \arctan \frac{q}{D}, \quad t = \frac{pD}{\sqrt{D^2 + p^2}}, \quad r = \frac{qD}{\sqrt{D^2 + q^2}},$$

where β is the angle between the projection's central ray and the y axis, D is the distance of this point from the origin and $[p, q]$ is point where rays intersect 2D plane ω as shown in the Fig. 1. For $q = 0$ the cone-beam is equivalent to a fan-beam [2].

Analytical reconstruction algorithms have been developed to process continuous data without noise, based on the Fourier slice theorem, which states that the 1D Fourier transform of a projection at θ is equal to the 2D Fourier transform of a slice through an object at an angle θ with the x axis [3]. This theorem applies to parallel-beam projections.

Theorem 1 (Fourier slice). *Let $f(x, y)$ defined on \mathbb{R}^2 be an absolutely integrable function in the natural domain of the Radon transform. For any $\theta \in (0, 2\pi)$ it is true that*

$$\begin{aligned} F(u, v) &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) e^{-i2\pi(ux+vy)} dx dy \\ &= \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y) e^{-i2\pi\omega(x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta)} dx dy = P_\theta(\omega), \end{aligned}$$

where $[u, v] \in \mathbb{R}^2$ are spatial frequencies along the x and y axes and $\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ represents the frequency of the function along t axis [2,3].

Definition 2 (Filtered Backprojection). For an absolutely integrable function $f(x, y)$ defined on \mathbb{R}^2 the Filtered Backprojection (FBP) is given as

$$f(x, y) = \int_0^\pi \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} P_\theta(\omega) e^{i2\pi\omega t} H(\omega) d\omega d\theta = \int_0^\pi \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p_\theta(\alpha) h(t - \alpha) d\alpha d\theta, \quad (1)$$

where $t = x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta$, $H(\omega)$ is the frequency characteristic of the filter and $h(t)$ is its inverse Fourier transform [2,3].

For FBP, it is sufficient to take only projections from the interval $(0, \pi)$, because $p_\theta(t) = p_{\theta+\pi}(-t)$ [1]. It is acknowledged that real-world data are discrete and degraded by noise. However, it has been demonstrated that discrete approximations can yield satisfactory results [3].

Fan-beam projections can be reconstructed using FBP, where we express each ray of the fan-beam dataset as a ray in a parallel projection geometry [2]. The second option is to use weighted backprojection. The

Eq. (1) describing the FBP for the parallel-beam is expanded to a circular scan, and the function $f(x, y)$ is expressed in polar coordinates (r, ϕ) [2]. Then the weighted back projection can be expressed as

$$f(r, \phi) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} \left(1 + \frac{r}{D^2} \sin(\beta - \phi) \right)^{-2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p_\theta(\alpha) \frac{D}{\sqrt{D^2 + t^2}} h(t - \alpha) d\alpha d\theta.$$

Projections obtained in cone-beam geometry can be reconstructed using the most well-known algorithm, Feldkamp-David-Kress (FDK) [28]. The FDK algorithm was designed for circular trajectories and is an extension of the weighted backprojection fan-beam to three dimensions. The cone projections are weighted by the cosine of the angle between the given ray and the central ray, a 1D ramp filter is applied, and finally, the weighted backprojection is performed. Each line of the cone projection is treated as a fan-beam projection [29].

For accurate reconstruction, the FDK algorithm requires precise knowledge of the scan geometry. Even small deviations or misalignments can lead to reconstruction artifacts and degraded image quality. In addition to correct source-detector distances and trajectory parameters, proper alignment of the system is essential, such as the central ray being orthogonal to the detector plane and the axis of rotation being parallel to the detector columns, as discussed by Ferrucci [11]. These constraints underscore the importance of a well-calibrated acquisition setup and highlight the need for calibration methods capable of detecting and compensating for geometric misalignments or deviations in the scan geometry.

3.2. Artifacts

In tomographic imaging, artifacts are distortions in reconstructed images that do not correspond to the true structure of the scanned object and are commonly classified as geometric, physical, or system-related [1].

This work addresses geometric artifacts caused by inaccuracies in the spatial configuration of the imaging system, such as misalignment of the X-ray source, detector, or axis of rotation. Because tomographic reconstruction relies on an accurate geometric model, even small deviations can result in pronounced artifacts, including blurring, double edges, and spatial misalignment. The calibration method proposed in this study is specifically designed to mitigate these geometry-induced artifacts.

Physical and system-related artifacts are mentioned only for completeness and are not addressed by the proposed calibration. These artifacts originate from X-ray-matter interactions or hardware imperfections and require different correction strategies. An illustrative overview

Fig. 2. Measurement geometry of the experiment. Each component of the CT system has its own coordinate system and axis of rotation. (a) Photograph of the actual experimental setup. (b) Schematic representation of the CT geometry, including the X-ray source, moving plate, and detector.

Table 2
Summary of types of artifacts, adapted from [1].

Type of artifact	Scan geometry	Category
Ring artifacts	Parallel, fan, cone	Scanner
Bad or hot pixels	Parallel, fan, cone	Scanner
Beam hardening	Parallel, fan, cone	Physical
Motion artifacts	Parallel, fan, cone	Physical
Metal artifacts	Parallel, fan, cone	Physical
Scatter	Parallel, fan, cone	Physical
Centering	Parallel, fan, cone	Geometry
Angular positioning errors	Parallel, fan, cone	Geometry
X-ray magnification	Fan, cone	Geometry
Horizontal or in-plane midline offset	Fan, cone	Geometry
Vertical centering	Cone	Geometry

of the main artifact types are provided in Table 2, with emphasis on geometric misalignment.

4. Acquisition hardware

The data acquisition system comprises a portable X-ray source and a flat-panel detector, with a rotating platform positioned between them to hold and rotate the sample during scanning. This configuration enables the acquisition of a comprehensive set of projections by precisely manipulating the sample’s rotational angles, a prerequisite for tomographic reconstruction.

To ensure optimal reconstruction accuracy, the system is calibrated using a 3D-printed calibration phantom. This calibration determines optimal geometric parameters, thereby minimizing reconstruction errors and reducing imaging geometric artifacts. The overall scanning arrangement is illustrated in Fig. 2, where the right side shows the simplified geometric model used later in the calibration process (see Section 5.2), and the left side shows the actual configuration.

Table 3 provides a summary of the X-ray source (Baltspot LLX200-DA), detector (SCANRAY 2329), and sample rotation system (EQ8 PRO astronomical mount), respectively. The EQ8 PRO mount, originally designed for precise tracking and positioning of telescopes, is repurposed in this setup to provide accurate, stable rotation of the sample during scanning.

To evaluate the impact of geometric calibration on reconstructed image quality, a mechanical gearbox component was scanned (as shown in Fig. 2). The object features distinct structural elements, including flat metal surfaces, cylindrical shafts, and a fine-toothed gear, which render it suitable for visual assessment of reconstruction improvements. The scanned mechanical gearbox component measures 71 mm × 64 mm × 61 mm. This object was chosen because the mobile X-ray scanning

methodology is primarily developed for industrial field applications, where metallic components are typically examined. Therefore, we selected a readily available representative mechanical part, which is suitable for both demonstration and validation of the proposed calibration approach.

All measured data can be found in the Data availability 7 at the end of the text. The reconstruction of the acquired projection data was performed in MATLAB using the ASTRA toolbox [33,34], which implements the FDK algorithm, thus enabling a direct comparison of the reconstructed volumes before and after the application of the calibration procedure.

In this work, calibration results were used to inform a preprocessing procedure that rotated, cropped, and transformed the projection data in order to rectify their geometry prior to reconstruction. After that, the calibrated geometry was entered into the ASTRA code using its simplified interface for circular cone-beam scans. This interface requires only the SOD and origin-to-detector distances, projection angles along a circular trajectory, spacing between detector rows and columns, and an optional lateral shift of the axis of rotation (AoR).

The mobile CT system used in this work was entirely assembled and commissioned by our team from commercially available components originally designed for different purposes. Since no unified control software was available, a custom application was developed to synchronize the operation of the X-ray source, detector, and rotation stage, ensuring correct timing and safe acquisition.

5. Calibration method

In radiography, it is difficult to adjust the object’s position so that its axis of rotation is exactly perpendicular to the central ray and parallel to the detector columns. The exact positions of the AoR and the principal point (the intersection of the central ray with the detector) are essential for an accurate 3D reconstruction. In the following section, we present a general procedure for determining the exact AoR by generating ellipses formed by the rotation of the calibration phantom containing steel spheres. The main task is to determine the most accurate SDD and ODD (see Fig. 2).

The following sections provide a general description of the proposed calibration approach. The method has been developed as a simplified yet robust alternative to conventional phantom-based procedures. It relies on analytically defined ellipses and area-based evaluation rather than multi-parameter numerical models. For clarity, the complete calibration and reconstruction workflow is summarized in the flowchart presented in Fig. 3.

Table 3
 Technical parameters of X-ray source Baltospot LLX200-DA [30], detector SCANRAY 2329 [31] and moving plate EQ8 [32].

X-ray source Baltospot LLX200-DA			
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
High voltage range:	5 to 200 kV	Maximum anode power:	900 W
Tube current range:	0.5 to 12 mA	Temp. switch:	70 °C
Beam angle:	60° × 40°	Weight (without rings):	18.1 kg
Focal spot size:	1.5 × 1.5 mm ²	Steel penetration at max:	44 mm
Inherent filtration:	0.8 mm Be	Tubehead:	Metal-Ceramic
Anode cooling type:	Air	Control unit:	DC1
detector SCANRAY 2329			
Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
Active dimension:	230 x 289 mm	Exposure time:	0.1 - 180 sec
Scintillator type:	Gadox	Battery life:	8 h
Pixel pitch:	75 μm	Voltage range:	40 - 450 kV
Number of pixels:	3072 × 3840 px	Weight (with battery):	3.4 kg
Panel size:	322 x 355 x 17 mm	Dynamic range:	2 ¹⁶
moving plate EQ-8			
Parameter	Value		
Load capacity:	50 kg		
Mount Head Weight:	25.8 kg		
Power Requirement:	DC 11 - 16 V/4A		
Motors:	0.9° hybrid stepper motor		
Transmission:	435:1 worm drive + 256 micro-step/0.9° stepper motor		
Resolution:	44,544,000 counts/rev, approx 0.03 arc-second		
Maximum Slewing Speed:	3.7° per second		

Fig. 3. Flowchart illustrating the individual steps of the proposed calibration process using a 3D printed phantom.

5.1. Calibration phantom

In designing a calibration phantom for radiography, the choice of material proved critical for image quality. The phantom must permit adequate transmission of X-rays whilst concurrently preserving high contrast with the embedded calibration elements. Consequently, the radiographic properties of the printing material directly impact the visibility and segmentation accuracy of the projected features. Consequently, several widely utilized 3D printing polymers were evaluated to assess their suitability for this application. A Prusa MK3 printer with Prusament filament was used for 3D printing.

During the development phase, a range of calibration phantoms were tested, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The designs differed not only in the spatial arrangement and geometry of the embedded steel spheres, but also in the 3D printing material. Although all variants allowed for basic calibration, the third configuration (right in Fig. 4) was determined to be the most suitable in terms of visibility and practical usability.

The utilization of PETG as a potential phantom material was considered. However, even at the elevated radiation levels required for scanning metal components, the internal structure remained distinct, thereby reducing the visibility of the embedded spheres. As demonstrated in Fig. 4 (left and middle), the disparity in contrast between the steel calibration spheres and the surrounding PETG material is in-

adequate. Consequently, PLA was identified as a more appropriate material due to its superior X-ray transparency and enhanced contrast performance. A thorough analysis of the interaction between X-rays and common 3D printing materials, including attenuation characteristics, is presented in the work of Beltran [35], which supports the observed differences in image quality. However, the X-ray source and its output parameters remained constant throughout all measurements. In this context, the impact of detector characteristics on image quality is negligible; any substantial variations in results are predominantly ascribed to the phantom design and material properties.

The most suitable phantom for calibration was found to be a cylinder containing 12 steel spheres (5 mm in diameter) arranged in a helical pattern. This cylindrical design ensures consistent visibility of the calibration points across various projection angles, making it ideal for robust geometric calibration. The steel spheres used in this phantom comply with ISO 3290-1:2014, Grade G10, ensuring high dimensional accuracy (on the order of tenths of micrometers) required for precise geometric analysis. The arrangement of the calibration spheres along a helical path, with a sufficiently large angular step between the steel spheres, ensures that their projections do not overlap. The use of twelve spheres was selected as an optimal compromise between geometric coverage and segmentation clarity. The first sphere defines a reference position, while the remaining eleven are distributed at 30° intervals to

Fig. 4. Phantom samples used in the experiments. (a)-(b) PETG phantoms representing different design iterations; these were imaged using a different detector with characteristics similar to the detector described in Section 4 and are shown here for illustration purposes. (c) PLA phantom used for calibration. (d) Final 3D-printed calibration phantom used in the calibration process.

maintain an asymmetric pattern. A symmetric arrangement could lead to ambiguous projections near principal vertices, where positional changes are minimal, increasing the risk of accumulated reconstruction errors. Conversely, a higher number of spheres would lead to overlapping projections of steel spheres, thereby complicating the segmentation process and reducing calibration robustness. Consequently, the ensuing segmentation process, described in Section 5.2.2, can be executed without encountering any complications. The angular step is considered adequate provided that the calibration spheres generate non-overlapping elliptical orbits during the scan. This condition depends on the tilt of the phantom's z' axis relative to the detector plane. In our case, the helix has a height of 144 mm and a radius of 30 mm. The calibration phantom's geometry is scale-invariant, meaning that its proportions and relative marker positions remain unchanged when uniformly scaled. This allows the overall size to be adjusted according to the geometry of the CT system. Three circular through-holes were incorporated into the phantom to facilitate its placement onto the rotation stage. This design facilitates alignment and ensures that the phantom can be positioned as close as possible to the center of the detector prior to scanning. The configuration of the calibration phantom is illustrated in Fig. 4 on the right. The STL file of the calibration phantom used in this study is provided in the Data availability 7 at the end of the text.

5.2. Mathematical computation of geometric parameters for reconstruction

This section provides a detailed description of the procedure for determining the parameters required for the accurate calculation of SDD and SOD necessary for tomographic reconstruction. In the initial phase, a set of 12 calibration images of the phantom with steel spheres is considered. The precise geometry of the ellipse, including its shape and surface characteristics, is established. The axis of the phantom and the perpendicular projection of the beam coming from the X-ray are then calculated from the centers of the elliptical motion paths of each sphere. The alignment of these ellipse centers defines the orientation of the phantom axis. At the same time the perpendicular projection of the beam is obtained as the normal to this direction in the detector plane. A more detailed explanation of the underlying geometric and stochastic model is provided in Section 5.2.2

The second part then describes the creation of a virtual model of the calibration phantom projections using the center-projection model with the given parameters. The last phase of the process is the optimization phase, in which the parameters of the real model are adjusted to match

with the parameters of the ideal virtual model, which is described in Sections 5.2.3 and 5.2.4.

5.2.1. Exact description of the geometry

To calibrate the portable CT system, we introduce two geometric models. First, we present an idealised, simplified configuration (see Fig. 5) to demonstrate the fundamental calibration principles. We then move on to a more complex model (see Fig. 6) that accounts for real variations in the system.

In the ideal model, we consider a rectangular coordinate system (t, s, r) , where the detection plane lies in the (t, r) plane and the s -axis is perpendicular to it, corresponding to the direction of the central X-ray beam. The rotation axis is identical to the r -axis; that is, it lies in the detection plane and is perpendicular to the t -direction. The X-ray source emits a central beam along the s -axis, which intersects the detector at $[D_x, D_y]$ (principal point).

During calibration, it is necessary to consider not only the system's geometric arrangement but also the position and orientation of the calibration phantom relative to the coordinate system of the detector (t, s, r) . In particular, the phantom's height displacement h_0 in the direction of the AoR o' and its initial rotation θ'_0 about the AoR are important parameters. These parameters determine the appearance of the projections of the phantom, so their reliable determination is essential for an accurate geometric model on which the calibration is based. Using these two parameters o' and θ'_0 , the optimization problem described in Section 5.2.4 can be used to obtain the SOD and SDD in the ideal model. In addition to the simplified geometric spatial model as a whole, Fig. 5 shows views of the various planes. These planes are described and labelled in the Table 4.

The ideal model provides an initial basis for a generalized description that accounts for geometric variations in the physical system. Firstly, the detector plane may be pitched to its ideal orientation by an angle θ_0 , which introduces a systematic angular variation in the projection geometry. Secondly, the symmetry axis of the cylindrical phantom z' may not be perfectly aligned with the system's rotation axis. In this case, the projection of the rotation axis o' does not coincide with the r -axis, which forms the coordinate system of the ideal detector (t, s, r) . These misalignments must be accounted for during calibration to ensure accurate geometric modelling and artifact-free image reconstruction. Furthermore, in the generalized case, the central projection beam is perpendicular to the projection of the rotation axis o , because the AoR o' can generally be deflected from its ideal position. The entire generalized model is shown in Fig. 6. The parameters that will be determined by calibration are listed in the Table 5.

Table 4

An overview of the planes shown in the ideal geometric model depicted in the Fig. 5 and their geometric meaning.

Color and location	What the plane represents	Functional name
3D top	Full spatial representation of the CT system components	Ideal model geometry
■ middle - (b)	Plane containing the center of the sphere and its projection on the detector and passing through the origin of the coordinates $[D_x, D_y]$	Projection Plane
■ bottom left - (c)	Plane defined by the boundary rays passing tangentially around the sphere, total visual angle 2β	Visual plane
■ bottom right - (d)	The detector plane - the (t, r) plane where the projection appears	Detector plane

Fig. 5. Spatial geometry of the simplified model. The phantom axis z' is assumed to coincide with the rotation axis o' , and the projection of the rotation axis o' coincides with the coordinate axis r , which is part of the detector coordinate system (t, s, r) with its origin at $[D_x, D_y]$. (a) Three-dimensional view of the ideal geometric model showing the spatial arrangement of the CT system components. (b) Projection plane containing the center of the sphere and its projection onto the detector, passing through the origin $[D_x, D_y]$. (c) Visual plane defined by the boundary rays passing tangentially to the sphere, corresponding to the visual angle 2β . (d) Detector plane represented by the (t, r) coordinate system, where the projection is formed. The meaning and geometric interpretation of the individual planes are summarized in Table 4. The definitions of all variables used in the figure are provided in the Nomenclature.

Fig. 6. Spatial geometry for the general case, where the phantom axis is not identical to the rotation axis, the detector is offset from its ideal position by an angle θ_o , and the projection of the rotation axis o' differs from the coordinate axis z of the ideally positioned detector, as illustrated in Fig. 5. A complete list and description of the symbols used in this figure can be found in the Nomenclature.

Table 5
Parameters determined during the calibration process.

Symbol	Parameter
θ_r	angle of the projection of AoR
$[D_x, D_y]$	principal point
θ_o	detector tilt angle
θ'_y	angle of the AoR o' from the detector in the ideal position
θ'_z	angle of offset rotation of the AoR o'
θ'_o	initial angle of rotation of the phantom during the first projection
d'_o	translation of the phantom axis z' from AoR o'
d'_z	translation of the phantom axis z' in the direction of o'
SDD	Source-Detector Distance
SOD	Source-Object Distance

5.2.2. Alignment of rotation axis projection

The determination of the projection of the phantom's AoR is based on X-ray images acquired over a full 360° scan with a 30° angular step. The sufficient contrast between the steel spheres and the background enabled effective application of a global threshold of 0.6 for segmentation after min-max normalization of the data.

To enhance the segmentation accuracy and achieve more precise delineation of each sphere, a two-step thresholding approach was employed. Initially, global thresholding was employed to swiftly isolate the spheres from the background. Subsequently, adaptive local thresholding was applied within designated regions to refine segmentation results and improve pixel-level precision. For a selected region containing a sphere of radius r_s , the pixel neighborhood was defined as a square region with a side length of $4r_s$. The histogram of such a region displays a strongly bimodal distribution. Otsu's method was applied to determine the optimal threshold, as it maximizes the between-class variance of pixel intensity distributions. The mathematical basis of Otsu's method is outlined in the following text [36].

Let an image have a grayscale intensity range $[0, L - 1]$, and let $p(i)$ be the normalized histogram of the image. The total probability of oc-

currence of intensity levels is given by:

$$\sum_{i=0}^{L-1} p(i) = 1.$$

For a given threshold T , the probabilities of the two classes (background and foreground) are defined as:

$$\omega_1(T) = \sum_{i=0}^T p(i), \quad \omega_2(T) = \sum_{i=T+1}^{L-1} p(i).$$

The mean levels of the two classes are given by:

$$\mu_1(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^T ip(i)}{\omega_1(T)}, \quad \mu_2(T) = \frac{\sum_{i=T+1}^{L-1} ip(i)}{\omega_2(T)}.$$

The between-class variance is defined as:

$$\sigma_B^2(T) = \omega_1(T)\omega_2(T)(\mu_1(T) - \mu_2(T))^2.$$

Otsu's method finds the threshold T^* that maximizes the between-class variance:

$$T^* = \arg \max_T \sigma_B^2(T).$$

The method's computational complexity is relatively low, making it highly efficient. The output of this method is a set of binary images, where some of the segmented spheres can be seen in Fig. 7.

For each frame, rotating by 30°, we obtain the new position of each calibration sphere. The spheres are segmented using the previously described adaptive thresholding, and their centers of gravity (centers of ellipses) are calculated. Each steel sphere traces an elliptical path in the projection images as the phantom rotates, forming a distinct ellipse corresponding to its trajectory.

The centers of these ellipses then lie on the projection of the AoR, and by analyzing the ratio of the minor and major semi-axes, which reflects the ellipse's eccentricity caused by the projection angle, it is possible to determine the principal point $[D_x, D_y]$.

Fig. 7. Projections of the calibration phantom acquired with an angular step of 60°. The projection angle is indicated in the upper-right corner of each image. (a)-(e) Selected projection images at different rotation angles; the regions marked by small boxes indicate the cut-outs shown in detail in the middle row. (f)-(j) Magnified views of the corresponding cut-outs marked with a red frame. (k)-(o) Binary segmentations of the spheres obtained using Otsu's thresholding method.

As a first step, we derive the equations of the ellipses that are determined by the positions of the individual spheres of the phantom during rotation. The general equation of the ellipse is given by:

$$E(x, y) = a_{11}x^2 + 2a_{12}xy + a_{22}y^2 + 2a_{13}x + 2a_{23}y + a_{33} = 0 \quad (2)$$

We divide the Eq. (2) by absolute member a_{33} such as $b_{ii} = a_{ii}/a_{33}$ for $i = 1, 2$ and $b_{ij} = a_{ij}/2a_{33}$ for $i, j = 1, 2, 3, i \neq j$. Then we get:

$$b_{11}x^2 + b_{12}xy + b_{22}y^2 + b_{13}x + b_{23}y = -1 \quad (3)$$

Add the $[x_k, y_k]$ coordinates of the center of gravity for the motion of each phantom sphere into the equation (in our case, the rotation is equal to 30 degrees, so that $k = 1, \dots, 12$). This gives us an overdetermined system of linear equations for the unknown parameters that determine the equation of the ellipse.

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_1^2 & x_1y_1 & y_1^2 & x_1 & y_1 \\ x_2^2 & x_2y_2 & y_2^2 & x_2 & y_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{12}^2 & x_{12}y_{12} & y_{12}^2 & x_{12} & y_{12} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} b_{11} \\ b_{12} \\ b_{22} \\ b_{13} \\ b_{23} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -1 \\ -1 \\ \vdots \\ -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

Fig. 8 shows the individual positions of the computed centers of the sphere images as they are rotated in sequence. The next step is to find the center and the sizes of the major and minor semi-axes of each ellipse.

We perform a recomputation of the values a_{ij} in Eq. (2) using the values of b_{ij} in Eq. (3). We build a symmetrical matrix of conic sections

using these coefficients:

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & a_{13} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} & a_{23} \\ a_{13} & a_{23} & a_{33} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The geometry of the ellipse is analyzed through the submatrix of quadratic terms:

$$\mathbf{Q} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} \\ a_{12} & a_{22} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Firstly, we compute the coordinates of the centers (x_S, y_S) by these system of equations:

$$\mathbf{Q} \begin{pmatrix} x_S \\ y_S \end{pmatrix} = -\mathbf{b}, \text{ where } \mathbf{b} = \begin{pmatrix} a_{13} \\ a_{23} \end{pmatrix}.$$

The solution is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x_S \\ y_S \end{pmatrix} = -\mathbf{Q}^{-1}\mathbf{b}.$$

The centers of all the ellipses give the equation of the line, which is the image of the AoR of the object.

Then we compute the major and minor semi-axes of the ellipses. Eigen directions of the ellipse correspond to the eigenvectors of the matrix \mathbf{Q} , where the eigenvalues λ_1, λ_2 are the solutions of the characteristic equation:

$$\det(\mathbf{Q} - \lambda\mathbf{I}) = 0.$$

Fig. 8. Visualization of the calibration sphere positions and the estimation of the perpendicular ray projection. (a) All detected positions of the calibration spheres at different altitudes together with the corresponding ellipse centers determined from ellipse fitting; the projection of the rotation axis onto the detector plane is indicated by the vertical line, and the principal point is marked. (b) Example of determining the projection of the perpendicular ray by minimizing the ratio of the squared minor semi-axis to the squared major semi-axis, b^2/a^2 , as a function of the projection height.

The angle of rotation of the ellipse is given by:

$$\tan(2\theta) = \frac{2a_{12}}{a_{11} - a_{22}}.$$

The major axis length a and minor semi-axis length b are computed as:

$$a = \sqrt{\frac{-c}{\lambda_{\min}}}, \quad b = \sqrt{\frac{-c}{\lambda_{\max}}}, \quad \text{where } c = \frac{\det(\mathbf{A})}{\det(\mathbf{Q})}.$$

The second significant piece of information that can be obtained from the projections of the ellipses is the principal point $[D_x, D_y]$ in Fig. 8, left. This point is given as the center of the ellipse, whose minor and major semi-axis ratio is closest to zero, that is, $b/a = 0$ since $b = 0$. In order to identify the minima in these ratios, the squared ratio $b^2/a^2 = 0$ is utilised. We use the least-squares method to fit these ratios to a parabola and find its minimum. This method provides the position of the principal point $[D_x, D_y]$. The Fig. 8 on the right presents the calculated ratios and the interleaved parabola with its minimum.

In contrast to the majority of extant calibration schemes, the ratio of the ellipse semi-axes is employed analytically here to determine the intersection of the central beam with the detector plane, thereby enabling direct localization of the principal point without the need for external references.

5.2.3. Geometry of calibration sphere projections

Consider the situation in which we want to determine the optimal projection of a calibration sphere onto the detector. The ideal projection

of a calibration sphere onto the detector is geometrically described by Fig. 5. The sphere is defined by its center and radius, and we know the angle α the SDD forms with the projection beam passing through the center S of this sphere. Let S_p denote the projection of this center in the detector plane.

Let β denote the angle formed by the projection beam of the tangent points A, B (see Fig. 5) with the beam passing through S, S_p . These two points are projected as points A_p, B_p , forming the major axis of the elliptical projection of a sphere.

The coordinates of these projections A_p, B_p can be calculated from the resulting right-angled triangles as:

$$A_p = \tan(\alpha + \beta) \cdot SDD$$

$$B_p = \tan(\alpha - \beta) \cdot SDD$$

The projection of the center of the ellipse is denoted as the point S_p and $S_p = \tan(\alpha) \cdot SDD$. It is important to note that, because of the properties of central projection, this is not the center of the projected ellipse. The center of the projection ellipse E_p lies at the midpoint of the segment A_p, B_p as can be seen in the Fig. 5.

The next task is to determine the size of the minor semi-axis of the elliptical projection of a sphere. To do this, it is enough to know the projection of one general point on the ellipse. The tangent points M, N that lie on the perpendicular to the diameter of the calibration sphere form the chord MN . Point M is projected on the circumference of the ellipse as point $X = [x_e, y_e]$, as shown in Fig. 5. This point X must lie on

the perpendicular line passing through S_p to the major axis of the ellipse. After that, it is very simple to calculate the size of the semi-minor axis from the general equation of the ellipse.

If the ellipse has a general center at $E_p = [e_x, e_y]$, its equation is:

$$\frac{(x - e_x)^2}{a_p^2} + \frac{(y - e_y)^2}{b_p^2} = 1$$

From this equation, after substituting for the coordinates x, y of the general point $X = [x_e, y_e]$, the size of the minor semi-axis b_p can be expressed as:

$$b_p^2 = \frac{(y_e - e_y)^2 a_p^2}{a_p^2 - (x_e - e_x)^2}$$

Thus:

$$b_p = \sqrt{\frac{(y_e - e_y)^2 a_p^2}{a_p^2 - (x_e - e_x)^2}}$$

The last value we need for the optimization problem is the area of the ellipse. It can be calculated using the following equation:

$$S_e = \pi \cdot A_p \cdot B_p$$

For each calibration sphere, we calculate key parameters of its elliptical projection using the steps outlined below. We will provide the lengths of the major and minor semi-axes a_p, b_p , the area of the ellipse S_e , and the coordinates of the projection center E_p .

The ideal values calculated in this manner are subsequently incorporated into the following phase, where they are used in an optimization problem to determine the essential parameters for the reconstruction process.

5.2.4. Optimization of reconstruction parameters

In the preceding Sections 5.2.1–5.2.3, the spatial geometry of the entire CT system has been comprehensively delineated. The projection of the rotation axis and the perpendicular beam onto the detector have been determined, and the positions of projected centers of calibration spheres for both the measured projections and the virtual mathematical model have been obtained.

In order to accurately reconstruct the obtained projections using the FDK algorithm described in Section 3 and to eliminate as many geometric artifacts as possible, it is necessary to obtain the SDD , SOD parameters. The parameters in question are obtained via a multi-level optimization problem that minimizes the deviations between the actual projections of the calibration spheres and their virtual representations. The following parameters need to be optimized. The geometric meaning of these parameters can also be seen in Fig. 6.

Initial values

- $\theta_o = 0^\circ$ detector tilt angle
- $\theta'_y = 0^\circ$ angle between the AoR o' from the detector plane in the ideal position
- $\theta'_z = 0^\circ$ angle of offset rotation of the AoR o'
- $\theta_o = 180^\circ$ initial rotation of the phantom during the first projection (we consider the position of the lowest calibration sphere), the phantom is in a basic position if lowest sphere is positioned closest to the detector plane as in Fig. 5 where $\theta'_o = 0^\circ$
- $d'_o = 0$ translation of phantom axis z' from AoR o' .
- $d'_z = -50$ translation of the phantom axis z' in the direction of o' ,
- $SDD = 950$ mm Source-Detector Distance, measured approximately with a tape measure
- $SOD = 800$ mm Source-Object Distance, measured approximately with a tape measure

The optimization method takes as inputs the data obtained in stage one of our research, such as S_e, E_p, a_p, b_p , and θ_e . For each phantom projection acquired every 30 degrees, the image is preprocessed using the

procedure described in Section 5.2.2, and the projections of each calibration sphere are identified as ellipses. The major and minor semi-axes, center coordinates, and area of each ellipse are calculated as described in Section 5.2.3. Additionally, the position and orientation of the AoR are known.

To address this sensitivity, a two-step optimization procedure was employed. The optimization is based on a parameter search that compares the measured and virtual projections of the calibration phantom and iteratively traverses the space of eight geometric parameters.

In the first phase, the goal is to determine the values of SDD and SOD . The objective function is minimized by reducing the difference between the measured dimensions of the elliptical projections of the calibration spheres and their ideal projections as provided by the model in Sections 5.2.2 and 5.2.3.

In the second phase, optimization is performed over the remaining geometric parameters: $\theta_o, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, d'_o$, and d'_z . In this stage, the error is calculated as the deviation between the centers of the real and virtual projections of the calibration spheres.

Since the adjustments to these parameters can slightly affect the values of SDD and SOD , a third optimization phase is performed where all parameters are optimized, during which the deviation between the centers of the real and virtual projections of the calibration spheres is minimized again, as in the second phase. Experimentally, it has been shown that this final step may yield different optimal parameter sets, corresponding to different local minima of the objective function. This is a consequence of optimizing eight parameters simultaneously, which naturally leads to a search space with multiple local minima. However, the resulting optima tend to differ only marginally — by at most a few tenths of a degree for angular parameters and a few millimeters for positional parameters. These differences can be considered negligible in the context of the overall system geometry. These final values were then used as inputs in the 3D reconstruction process. The whole optimization algorithm is described in Algorithm 1 and in Appendix A.

Given the greater number of local minima in this particular optimization problem, it is also beneficial to assess the accuracy of the optimal solution. In the context of multi-level geometry optimization, the presence of two objective functions requires the construction of two metrics to assess the accuracy of the solution. In the first step, we calculate the average differences between the centers of virtual and measured ellipses using the Euclidean norm:

$$S_{mean} = \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^{12} \sum_{j=1}^{12} \|S_{ij}^{DataVirtual} - S_{ij}^{Data}\|.$$

In the following step, the mean disparity in area between the virtual and real ellipses is to be calculated by means of the Euclidean norm:

$$S_{mean} = \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^{12} \sum_{j=1}^{12} \|S_{ij}^{DataVirtual} - S_{ij}^{Data}\|$$

The calculation of the mean area for the virtual ellipses is required, as well as the determination of the diameter of the aforementioned average ellipse. We assume that this ellipse is very close to the circle:

$$D_{mean} = 2 \sqrt{\pi^{-1} \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^{12} \sum_{j=1}^{12} S_{ij}^{DataVirtual}}.$$

To determine the accuracy of the solution, we compute the ratio r_1 of the average deviation of the centers with respect to the average of the average virtual ellipse and the ratio r_2 of the average difference between the contents of the virtual and real ellipse and the perimeter of the average virtual ellipse:

$$r_1 = 100 \cdot \frac{S_{mean}}{D_{mean}}, \quad r_2 = 100 \cdot \frac{S_{mean}}{\pi D_{mean}}. \quad (4)$$

The overall calibration strategy integrates analytical formulation with area-based optimization, yielding a straightforward, reproducible,

and noise-resistant procedure. This combination provides a practical alternative to existing phantom-based calibration methods. The latter typically rely on complex geometric models and extensive numerical fitting.

Algorithm 1 Multi-level geometry optimization.

```

1: Inputs:
   projections of calibration phantom
2: Initiation:
    $\theta_o = 0, \theta'_y = 0, \theta'_z = 0, \theta'_o = 180, d'_o = 0, d'_z = -50,$ 
    $SDD = 950, SOD = 800$ 
3: Determine the step size for each parameter - range of test values
4: Data = PHANTOMDATA(projections of calibration phantom)
5: for  $SDD, SOD$  in search interval do
6:   DataVirtual = PURPOSEFUNCTION(Data,  $S_{all}, \theta_r, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, \theta_o,$ 
    $SDD, SOD, d'_o, d'_z, D_x, D_y$ )
7:   Minimize area difference between real and virtual ellipses  $\triangleright$ 
   Other parameters remain unchanged
8:   break if minimum found
9: end for
10: for  $\theta_o, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, d'_o, d'_z$  in search interval do
11:   DataVirtual = PURPOSEFUNCTION(Data,  $S_{all}, \theta_r, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, \theta_o,$ 
    $SDD, SOD, d'_o, d'_z, D_x, D_y$ )
12:   Minimize center deviation between real and virtual ellipses  $\triangleright$ 
    $SDD, SOD$  remain unchanged
13:   break if minimum found
14: end for
15: for  $SDD, SOD, \theta_o, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, d'_o, d'_z$  in new search interval (possibility to set a smaller step) do
16:   DataVirtual = PURPOSEFUNCTION(Data,  $S_{all}, \theta_r, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, \theta_o,$ 
    $SDD, SOD, d'_o, d'_z, D_x, D_y$ )
17:   Minimize center deviation between real and virtual ellipses
18:   break if minimum found
19: end for
20: return  $SDD, SOD$ 

```

The proposed calibration procedure has modest computational requirements and can be executed on standard desktop-class hardware. All experiments were performed on conventional office PCs equipped with either an Intel Core i5 or an AMD Ryzen 5 CPU, with comparable performance observed on both platforms. The implementation was realized in MATLAB. Image preprocessing requires approximately 1 min, while the optimization step takes approximately 2 min for 600 iterations. No specialized hardware or operating system is required, which makes the method suitable for low-cost and portable CT setups intended for field deployment.

6. Results and discussion

The calibration process produced stable and consistent results across multiple optimization runs. Four independent optimizations were performed, each using a different iteration step size selected from the range 0.1 to 0.025. In each case, the variable was recalculated to maintain consistency with the corresponding angular or distance units. The final geometric parameters presented in Table 6 exhibited minimal variance, confirming that the parameter space yields robust and consistent solutions despite spanning eight interdependent variables. Other optimization solutions are shown in Appendix B. All optimization experiments were tested on the same inputs. It has been noted that minor discrepancies between locally optimal parameter sets (typically within 0.2° for rotations and 1–8 mm for distances) were negligible in terms of their effect on image reconstruction quality.

Only 12 calibration projections were used, as increasing their number did not yield a noticeable improvement in calibration accuracy. For comparison, six projections resulted in a rotation axis deviation of 0.259° and principal point coordinates [1064.8, 1194.5]; eight projections gave 0.238°, [1065.5, 1195.1]; and twelve projections produced

Table 6
Optimal parameters found by calibrating the phantom.

Parameter	Value
θ_r - angle of the projection of rotation axis	0.25053°
$[D_x, D_y]$ - principal point	[1065.1064, 1195.1345] px
θ_o - detector tilt angle	-0.65°
θ'_y - angle of the axis of the rotary table from the detector in the ideal position	0°
θ'_z - angle of offset rotation of the rotary table axis	11.7°
θ'_o - initial angle of rotation of the phantom during the first projection	168.15°
d'_o - translation of the phantom axis z' from AoR o'	1.4 mm
d'_z - translation of the phantom axis z' in the direction of o'	-49.1 mm
SDD - Source-Detector Distance	981 mm
SOD - Source-Object Distance	827 mm

0.251°, [1065.1, 1195.1]. These results show that variations in the rotation axis and principal point remain within tenths of a pixel, indicating sub-pixel precision. Therefore, using additional projections would not provide a measurable improvement in calibration accuracy.

To verify the accuracy of the optimal solution, we used the ratios defined in Eq. (4). Since the largest difference in local solutions is in the distances of SDD and SOD , we calculated the ratios for a range of initialization variables: the SDD in the interval (980, 990) and the SOD in the interval (825, 835), i.e., one percentile of possible input error. The remaining parameters were set to the same values as our best solution, as shown in Table 6. If we observe the ratio r_1 , then for all the starting values from these intervals, this ratio is on average 2.45%, which is an acceptable result from a statistical point of view. For the ratio r_2 , we get an average value of about 22%, which means that the number of pixels on the boundary of the real ellipses varies by 22 percent on average. This value may seem relatively large, but given that the ellipses have an average area of 4900 px, only 250 of which on average comprise the border, the change is only 1.122% pixels.

To further support the interpretation of these results, the obtained calibration metrics were recalculated into physical units (millimeters) based on the known geometry of the calibration phantom, where each steel sphere has a diameter of 2.5 mm. The quantitative estimation was performed as follows:

$$\sqrt{\frac{2.5^2}{4900} \times (4900 - 60)} \approx 2.485 \text{ mm}$$

This expression represents the effective radius of the projected sphere in pixel units, where 4900 px corresponds to the average ellipse area and 60 px represents approximately 1.12% of that area. The term (4900 - 60) therefore accounts for the observed variability of the ellipse boundary across projections, as discussed above, and defines the effective, reliable area used for quantitative estimation. To determine the corresponding physical scale, the pixel size relative to the real sphere diameter can be expressed as:

$$\sqrt{\frac{2.5^2 \pi}{4900}} = 0.0633 \text{ mm/px.}$$

Given that the mean positional deviation of the detected sphere centers was 1.93 pixels, the positional accuracy in millimeters is:

$$0.0633 \text{ mm/px} \times 1.93 \text{ px} = 0.122 \text{ mm.}$$

The value of 1.93 px represents the mean deviation of the detected sphere centers from their ideal positions after calibration, i.e., the average residual misalignment remaining in the reconstructed geometry. This quantitative evaluation shows that the positional accuracy of the reconstructed sphere centers is approximately 0.12 mm, confirming that the achieved calibration precision is consistent with the expected limits for the given CT setup.

Fig. 9. Visual results of the individual stages of the multi-level geometric optimization described in Algorithm 1. The projected centers of the measured and virtual spheres are shown. (a) First optimization stage minimizing the difference between the areas of the real and virtual ellipses, used to update the *SDD* and *SOD* parameters. (b) Second optimization stage minimizing the difference in the mean deviation between the real and virtual ellipses, using the *SDD* and *SOD* values obtained in the first stage. (c) Third optimization stage minimizing the difference in the center deviation between the real and virtual ellipses, in which all remaining geometric parameters are refined.

The difference between estimated and actual projections of sphere centers in cone-beam geometries is a documented issue [37], which can affect the accuracy of marker-based algorithms such as the calibration method presented herein. While this difference was deemed negligible in this case, it may have a larger impact on calibration results for other geometries. If this is the case, existing correction algorithms [37,38] can be incorporated into the processing workflow to improve the estimated locations of sphere center projections.

A visual inspection of the projection data confirmed a high degree of alignment between the measured and simulated ellipses. The centers of the projected spheres in the virtual model closely matched their real counterparts, thereby validating the calibrated system geometry. The area differences between corresponding ellipses remained minimal, further supporting the reliability of the optimization process. While the ellipse area is sensitive to segmentation quality and subject to higher uncertainty than center-to-center distances, it was used here as an additional consistency check. The behavior of the geometry based on parameter changes in a multi-level geometric optimization is shown in Fig. 9.

Achieving this level of precision was contingent on the design of the 3D-printed phantom. During the experimental procedure, it was established that the helical configuration of the printed PLA (Polylactic acid) with embedded steel spheres provided optimal contrast and visibility across all viewing angles. The mechanical stability and geometric regularity of the calibration spheres enabled reliable detection and tracking. The decision to use PLA rather than PETG was advantageous for X-ray transparency, leading to improved segmentation performance and reduced uncertainty in projection analysis. The 3D-printed phantom was prepared on a Prusa i3 MK3 3D printer. The tolerance accuracy of a standard Prusa i3 MK3 is 0.1 mm on the Z axis and 0.3 mm on the X and Y axes. Following the execution of additional calibrations, including Extrusion Multiplier calibration and Extruder Linearity correction, a reduction to as low as 0.05 mm on all axes is possible.

Although the overall performance of the system met expectations, certain limitations persist. The segmentation process still requires partial manual supervision, which can limit throughput. However, the successful calibration of this portable and low-cost setup demonstrates the viability of compact CT systems for practical applications.

This hypothesis is further substantiated by the reconstruction result depicted in Fig. 10 and another in the Appendix C, which clearly resolves the internal features of the scanned object. The reconstructed slice demonstrates that the geometric accuracy achieved through phantom-

based calibration is sufficient to enable high-quality volumetric reconstruction, even with a modest imaging setup. Some of the artifacts described in Section 3.2, such as blurring, double edges, and spatial shifts of sample structures, can be observed in the data reconstructed without calibration. After calibration, these errors in the data were reduced.

The proposed calibration method is primarily intended for industrial and field-based applications, where low-cost and portable CT systems can provide rapid qualitative insight into internal structures without the need for laboratory-grade equipment. Typical use cases include industrial inspections such as defect detection in castings, welds, and additively manufactured components, where fast on-site assessment is often more critical than metrological accuracy. In addition, the method is well suited for applications in archaeology and cultural heritage, where non-destructive imaging of fragile or unique objects is required and transportation to specialized CT facilities may be impractical or undesirable. In these scenarios, the ability to repurpose existing radiographic hardware into a portable CT system using an inexpensive calibration procedure significantly broadens access to tomographic imaging.

The primary limitation of the current implementation lies in the segmentation stage, which relies on manually adjusted parameters and therefore introduces a degree of operator dependency. Although this approach improves robustness under challenging imaging conditions, it limits full automation of the calibration workflow. The proposed calibration model itself does not assume an idealized cone-beam geometry; instead, it explicitly allows all geometric parameters to deviate from their nominal values. Consequently, potential inaccuracies are mainly related to segmentation quality and image noise rather than to limitations of the geometric model. Addressing these practical aspects through automated segmentation and further robustness improvements constitutes an important direction for future work.

In particular, the segmentation step, which is currently performed using manually tuned parameters, could be replaced by an automatic segmentation approach based on partial differential equations (PDE) [39,40]. Anisotropic diffusion models derived from the Perona-Malik framework provide a natural candidate, as they enable edge-preserving smoothing while suppressing noise, which is especially relevant for low-dose and low-contrast radiographic data. Such PDE-based methods could improve the stability of the segmentation under varying imaging conditions and reduce the need for operator intervention. In addition, extending the segmentation framework toward multi-scale formulations may facilitate adaptation of the proposed calibration method to higher-

Fig. 10. Example of one slice of reconstructed data in geometry $SDD = 981$ mm and $SOD = 827$ mm. (a) Representation of the slice plane through the gearbox. (b) Reconstruction of the original data, without calibration, here for $SDD = 950$ mm and $SOD = 800$ mm. (c) Reconstruction to crop the data so that the central ray, which is perpendicular to the rotation axis projection, is in the middle of the projection. (d) Reconstruction after obtaining the inclination of the projection of the AoR and the central ray perpendicular to this projection.

resolution CT systems, where increased sensitivity to noise and geometric imperfections poses additional challenges.

The application discussed in this work called for modest spatial resolution. There is potential for further work in terms of higher-resolution applications. These would necessitate the phantom to be printed at a smaller scale and with higher precision. Both of these changes can be accommodated by other consumer-level 3D-printing technologies, such as resin stereolithography. Professional 3D printing services can be utilized to reach even smaller scales and higher accuracy. However, the change in printing technology would require additional tests to evaluate the radio-opacity of the printing material. Adjustments to the phantom design may also be necessary for scales below a certain threshold.

7. Conclusion

This study proposes a geometric calibration approach that enables conversion of a basic X-ray imaging setup into a functional computed tomography system. Calibration is performed using a low-cost 3D-printed phantom with steel spheres arranged in a helical configuration, allowing estimation of key geometric parameters, including the SDD , SOD , and angular orientation. Using iterative optimization, the discrepancy between measured and simulated sphere projections is minimized, resulting in residual geometric deviations consistently below approximately one-fifth of a detector pixel, corresponding to sub-millimeter spatial accuracy in the reconstructed volume.

The proposed method achieves this level of accuracy while maintaining a relatively simple calibration formulation. In contrast to area-based ellipse fitting approaches, the calibration relies on point-based error metrics derived from detected sphere centers, reducing sensitivity to segmentation imperfections and lowering computational complexity. The complete optimization converges within a few minutes on standard desktop hardware, demonstrating that accurate geometric calibration can be achieved without specialized computational resources.

Experimental results show a clear reduction of geometry-induced artifacts, such as blurring and feature duplication, when comparing reconstructions before and after calibration. Although mechanical limitations of the portable setup impose practical accuracy bounds, the calibrated system produces stable and consistent reconstructions suitable for qualitative and quantitative analysis.

Overall, the combination of a portable X-ray source, a digital detector, and an inexpensive 3D-printed calibration phantom demonstrates that mobile CT systems with sub-pixel geometric accuracy can be realized using minimal hardware. The proposed method is therefore well-suited for field-based applications, including industrial inspection, non-destructive testing, and archaeology, where robustness, portability, and cost efficiency are prioritized over laboratory-grade metrological precision.

Data availability

The 3D model of the calibration phantom used in this study is openly available on Zenodo at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15592451>.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jana Procházková: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization; **Pavel Mikuláček:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology; **Marek Zemek:** Writing – review & editing; **Tomáš Zikmund:** Supervision; **Pavel Štarha:** Visualization, Software, Methodology.

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Pseudocodes of functions used in multi-level geometry optimization

Algorithm 2 Functions entering multi-level geometric optimization.

```

1: function PHANTOMDATA(phantom directory)
2:   for each frame  $l = 1$  to 12 do
3:     Flat-field correction of calibration phantom projections
4:     Calculating the area of a given ellipse -  $S_e$ 
5:     Obtaining the coordinates of the center of gravity of the ellipse -  $E_p$ 
6:     Calculation of the major and minor semi-axis of the ellipse -  $a_p, b_p$ 
7:     Ellipse orientation angle -  $\theta_e$ 
8:     Store  $S_e, E_p, a_p, b_p$  and  $\theta_e$  in Data
9:   end for
10:  return Data
11: end function
12: function SPHERESPROJECTION( $SDD, \vec{u}_d, \vec{v}_d, \vec{w}$ )
13:  Determine ellipse center  $E_p$ 
14:  Calculate major and minor semi-axis  $a_p, b_p$  of ellipse
15:  Calculate area of ellipse  $S_e$ 
16:  return  $E_p, a_p, b_p, S_e$ 
17: end function
18: function PURPOSEFUNCTION(Data,  $S_{all}$  - centers of spheres,  $\theta_r, \theta'_y, \theta'_z, \theta'_o, \theta_o, SDD, SOD, d'_o, d'_z, D_x, D_y$ )
19:  for each frame  $l = 1$  to 12 do
20:    for each sphere  $k = 1$  to 12 do
21:      Compute direction vector  $\vec{w}$  for the sphere
22:      Define sensor plane basis vectors  $\vec{u}_d, \vec{v}_d$ 
23:      Call SPHERESPROJECTION( $SDD, \vec{u}_d, \vec{v}_d, \vec{w}$ )
24:      Rotation of the center of the ball  $E_p$  to the ideal position of the detector plane
25:      Store ellipse center, axis and area in DataVirtual
26:    end for
27:  end for
28:  return DataVirtual
29: end function

```

B. Another optimal solutions from multi-level geometry optimization

Parameter	Value
θ_o - detector tilt angle	-0.7°
θ'_y - angle of the axis of the rotary table from the detector in the ideal position	0°
θ'_z - angle of offset rotation of the rotary table axis	11.925°
θ'_o - initial angle of rotation of the phantom during the first projection	167.925°
d'_o - translation of the phantom axis z' from AoR o'	1.4 mm
d'_z - translation of the phantom axis z' in the direction of o'	-49.125 mm
SDD - Source-Detector Distance	986 mm
SOD - Source-Object Distance	831 mm

Parameter	Value
θ_o - detector tilt angle	-0.7°
θ'_y - angle of the axis of the rotary table from the detector in the ideal position	0°
θ'_z - angle of offset rotation of the rotary table axis	11.9°
θ'_o - initial angle of rotation of the phantom during the first projection	167.95°
d'_o - translation of the phantom axis z' from AoR o'	1.4 mm
d'_z - translation of the phantom axis z' in the direction of o'	-49.125 mm
SDD - Source-Detector Distance	980 mm
SOD - Source-Object Distance	826 mm

Parameter	Value
θ_o - detector tilt angle	-0.6°
θ'_y - angle of the axis of the rotary table from the detector in the ideal position	0°
θ'_z - angle of offset rotation of the rotary table axis	12.1°
θ'_o - initial angle of rotation of the phantom during the first projection	167.8°
d'_o - translation of the phantom axis z' from AoR o'	1.4 mm
d'_z - translation of the phantom axis z' in the direction of o'	-49.1 mm
SDD - Source-Detector Distance	987 mm
SOD - Source-Object Distance	832 mm

C. Examples of gearbox reconstructions

Fig. C.11. Examples of several reconstructed slices obtained for the geometry with $SDD = 981$ mm and $SOD = 827$ mm. Rows (a)-(d) correspond to four different slice positions within the gearbox; each row therefore represents one fixed slice plane. Columns (i)-(iv) show the same slice reconstructed at different stages of the calibration process. In each row, (i) illustrates the position of the corresponding slice plane within the object, while (ii)-(iv) show the reconstructed slices. (ii) Reconstructions of the original data, without calibration, here for $SDD = 950$ mm and $SOD = 800$ mm. (iii) Reconstructions to crop the data so that the central ray, which is perpendicular to the rotation axis projection, is in the middle of the projection. (iv) Reconstructions after obtaining the inclination of the projection of the AoR and the central ray perpendicular to this projection.

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